

1 Title

2 Climate change experienced by life on Earth - drivers and mechanisms of future trends in microclimates

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4 Running title

5 Drivers and mechanisms of microclimate change

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16 **Title**

17 Climate change experienced by life on Earth - drivers and mechanisms of future trends in microclimates

18

19 **Abstract**

20 Microclimate affects organisms more directly than macroclimate, yet its long-term dynamics and
21 drivers of decadal microclimate changes remain underexplored in ecology and global change biology.
22 The general assumption is that microclimatic changes track macroclimate trends. However, changes in
23 meteorological conditions (e.g., cloud cover, wind patterns) and vegetation dynamics (e.g., canopy
24 thinning, desertification in drylands, shrub encroachment in the tundra) associated with climate change
25 can lead to locally divergent microclimate trends, thereby altering spatial variability. Understanding
26 and quantifying how climate change observed in standardized weather stations translates to fine-scale
27 microclimate change experienced by organisms, populations and communities is therefore essential for
28 predicting ecological responses to global environmental change.

29 This review examines how macroclimate change drives microclimate changes as experienced
30 by life on Earth - and how these micro-scale changes may, in turn, feed back into the regional and global
31 climate system. While our primary focus is on near-surface air and soil temperature - due to their
32 relevance to most terrestrial organisms and ecosystem processes - we also discuss other tightly linked
33 key climatic variables such as humidity and radiation. The review is structured around three pathways
34 of microclimate changes: (I) direct effects of changes in meteorological conditions, (II) indirect effects
35 via vegetation changes, and (III) feedbacks between microclimate and climate change. Using three
36 mechanistic model simulations in real-world landscapes, we exemplify and quantify the key
37 mechanisms that lead to divergent warming trends.

38 By integrating perspectives from meteorology, climate science, and ecology, this review advances our
39 understanding of the feedbacks between the biosphere, pedosphere, hydrosphere and atmosphere. We
40 argue that deciphering microclimate change is crucial to bridging the gap between climate science and
41 its application in global change biology.

42

43 **Keywords**

44 Vegetation-climate feedbacks, Biosphere-atmosphere interactions, Climate change ecology, Cold-air
45 pooling, Mesoclimate, Surface-energy balance, Inversions, Topoclimate

46

47 1. Introduction

48 Climate change is reshaping environmental conditions experienced by species worldwide (Pörtner et
49 al., 2021). Shifts in temperatures, precipitation, and the frequency and severity of extreme weather
50 events such as storms, heatwaves and wildfires are already affecting the distribution, phenology and
51 behaviour of organisms as well as the functioning of ecosystems around the globe (Grimm et al., 2013;
52 Muthukrishnan et al., 2025; Soifer et al., 2025), with even greater impacts projected for the coming
53 decades (IPBES, 2019). However, climate change projections are primarily based on global and
54 regional climate models that operate at coarse spatial resolutions (typically 1–100 km), which fail to
55 capture the **proximal** microclimatic conditions experienced by organisms (Christiansen et al., 2024;
56 Haesen, Lenoir, et al., 2023; Klinges et al., 2024) (See definitions in **Box 1**). As a result, our capacity
57 to predict biological responses and ecosystem functioning under future climates remains limited.

58 **Microclimates** are shaped by interactions of atmospheric conditions with land surface
59 properties such as topography and vegetation (see **Box 1** and **Box 2**), creating fine-scale heterogeneous
60 environments that can differ substantially - both spatially and temporally - from **macroclimate**
61 averages, which represent broader geographic regions (Geiger, 1966). In this review, we focus on
62 microclimate change - defined as long-term (decadal or longer) changes in near-surface temperature
63 and moisture conditions, including air temperature, soil moisture and relative air humidity. Importantly,
64 microclimate changes do not always mirror macroclimate changes. Shifts in average meteorological
65 conditions and extreme events directly influence microclimate warming rates, or indirectly do so by
66 altering vegetation structure, mortality and species composition (Seidl et al., 2017). In turn, climate-
67 driven vegetation changes - through changes in albedo, evapotranspiration, and biogenic volatile
68 organic compounds (BVOCs) - can influence meteorological processes such as cloud formation
69 (Duveiller et al., 2021). These vegetation–climate interactions create feedbacks (Luo et al., 2024a;
70 Miralles et al., 2025) that potentially diverge microclimate changes from macroclimatic changes. The
71 decoupling between microclimate and macroclimate changes leads to spatially and temporally variable
72 **offsets**, defined as the differences between microclimate and macroclimate (**Fig. 1, Box 1**). Beyond the
73 microclimate scale, spatial heterogeneity in warming rates also emerges at the mesoscale (1–100 km),
74 for instance through variations in elevational lapse rates, coastal–inland gradients, and continentality
75 effects (Mountain Research Initiative EDW Working Group, 2015). These **mesoclimate** processes
76 **modulate** the boundary conditions for microclimates and can **amplify** or **buffer** local warming, thereby
77 influencing the degree and direction of micro–macroclimate decoupling.

78 Despite their importance, microclimates are still often overlooked in climate change impact
79 assessments. Yet it is these proximal conditions that determine how individual organisms, populations,
80 and ecosystems respond to environmental change (Kemppinen et al., 2024; Kemppinen, Niittynen, le
81 Roux, et al., 2021; Körner & Hiltbrunner, 2018). Ignoring the fine-scale variability in microclimate

82 trends risks misjudging both the vulnerability and resilience of species and ecosystems to climate
83 change (Niittyinen et al., 2018). By integrating microclimate change into ecological research, we can
84 improve predictions of species distributions (Haesen, Lenoir, et al., 2023; Maclean & Early, 2023),
85 physiological responses (Buckley et al., 2023; Kearney & Leigh, 2024), and ecosystem functioning
86 (Beugnon et al., 2024; Virkkala et al., 2024) under climate change.

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90 *Fig. 1. Rates of change in microclimate temperatures at Caerthillian Cove, Lizard Peninsula, UK*
91 *(49.97° N, 5.21° W), from 1983 to 2015. Rates of change were derived for each grid cell by linear*
92 *regression on annual maximum air temperature (5 cm above ground). Interactions between terrain,*
93 *vegetation, and weather caused local warming rates to diverge from the regional macroclimate trend*
94 *(0.3°C over the ~3 decades). Maps were derived from data generated using the approach described in*
95 *Maclean (2020).*

96

97 Here, we review how, when, where and why microclimate change differs from macroclimate change,
98 and explore the drivers and feedbacks underlying these dynamics. We focus on three key pathways of
99 microclimate change (**Fig. 2**): (I) the influence of changing meteorological conditions on microclimate
100 change; (II) how vegetation responses to macroclimate change reshape local microclimate conditions;
101 and (III) how microclimates alter climate-change feedbacks. While our primary focus is on
102 microclimate temperature, we also discuss other key microclimate components - soil moisture, relative
103 humidity and radiation - as these are highly relevant to ecological processes and commonly studied and
104 additionally influence temperature. We deliberately exclude the direct effects of anthropogenic land-
105 use and land-cover change on microclimate (change) to isolate the effects of global climate change on

106 microclimate change, but acknowledge that also these other human-driven changes are crucial and
107 warrant further investigation. To better capture biologically relevant thermal conditions, we emphasize
108 indices such as daily and seasonal extremes instead of mean temperature (**Fig. 1**), as the latter can
109 obscure critical variability that drives ecological responses (Helmuth et al., 2010). By focusing on trends
110 in daily or seasonal extremes instead of annual means we also embrace asymmetric shifts that have been
111 observed for, e.g., day- vs. night-time or summer- vs. winter climate conditions (Cox et al., 2020; Shi
112 & Wu, 2025).

113 To illustrate the mechanisms that drive variation in microclimate change, we ran three different
114 case studies of model simulations using mechanistic microclimate models with air temperatures 5 cm
115 above ground as the output variable (Maclean, 2025). As a first case study across a 2 km × 2 km area
116 in the Pyrenees, we show how changing meteorological conditions influences near-surface
117 microclimate temperature by independently changing cloudiness, wind speed, soil moisture, air
118 humidity and snow presence. We looked at mean daily maxima and minima of the 10 warmest and
119 coldest days, respectively, using data from the year 2021. In a second study case in a deciduous forest
120 in New Hampshire, we demonstrate how long-term shifts in leaf phenology influence near-surface
121 below-canopy microclimate temperatures in spring. To isolate the effects of phenological change, we
122 fixed the weather input data to April 2019 and re-ran the mechanistic models using **Leaf Area Index**
123 (**LAI**) values from each year between 1982 and 2019. In a third case study focusing on a grassland
124 habitat (1 km × 1 km) in the Central Anatolian steppe, we assess how shrub and tree encroachment
125 alters near-surface below-canopy temperature minima and maxima, as in case study 1. To isolate the
126 effect of shrub and tree encroachment, we ran the mechanistic model twice: first on the current grassland
127 state of the site, and then after superimposing structural vegetation data from a nearby woodland site
128 onto the grassland's digital terrain model (more details are provided in the Supplementary Material).

129 Ultimately, by translating insights borrowed from meteorology and climate modelling into concepts
130 usable by ecologists, we aim to foster a cross-disciplinary understanding of microclimate ecology and
131 strengthen projections of biodiversity change and ecological management under rapid climate change.

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135 *Fig. 2. Conceptual figure representing the structure of this review. This review is structured around*
 136 *three pathways of microclimate change: (I) direct effects of changes in meteorological conditions (red),*
 137 *(II) indirect effects via vegetation changes (green) and (III) feedbacks between microclimate and global*
 138 *climate change (purple, dashed arrows).*

139

140 Box 1: Glossary

141 **Altitude:** The vertical distance of an object or point above mean sea level. Used for: Aircraft, cloud
 142 bases, or atmospheric layers - anything above the Earth's surface.

143 **Elevation:** The height of the land surface itself above mean sea level. Used for: Topographic or
 144 geographic features - mountains, plateaus, or study sites.

145 **Leaf Area Index (LAI):** The total one-sided leaf area per unit ground area (m² of leaf per m² of ground).

146 **Macroclimate:** The climate (average atmospheric conditions) in free-air conditions over a broad
 147 geographic region, largely independent of local influences such as topography, soil, and vegetation. It
 148 represents the climatic context within which meso-, and microclimates develop (Geiger, 1966). Spatial
 149 scale: ~ hundreds of km to continental / global scale.

150 **Mesoclimate:** The climate of an intermediate spatial scale, typically covering areas such as valleys,
 151 hillsides, or entire landscapes, situated between microclimate and macroclimate. It is impacted by meso-
 152 scale topographic features, land cover, distance to coastlines and local weather systems (Barry &
 153 Chorley, 2009). Spatial scale: ~ 1 km to several tens or a few hundred km.

154 **Microclimate:** The climate in a small, specific area near the Earth's surface (opposed to free-air
 155 macroclimate) characterised by temperature, moisture, wind, etc. conditions that differ from those in

156 the surrounding area, and importantly, directly influencing organisms (Barry & Blanken, 2016; De
157 Frenne et al., 2025). See also *proximal climate*. Spatial scale: ~ 1 cm to hundreds of metres.

158 **Microclimate modulation:** The change in amplitude of diurnal or seasonal temperature fluctuations
159 compared to reference macroclimate fluctuations. Microclimate **buffering** leads to a lower amplitude,
160 i.e., lower fluctuations, whereas **amplification** leads to a larger amplitude, i.e., larger fluctuations.
161 These can be quantified either by instantaneous or averaged *offsets*, or by linear regressions between
162 microclimate and macroclimate time series (Gril, Spicher, et al., 2023).

163 **Offset:** Difference between microclimate and reference macroclimate (De Frenne et al., 2021).
164 Typically, negative offsets signal microclimate being cooler than macroclimate.

165 **Proximal microclimate:** The microclimate close (proximal) to an organism, population or ecosystem
166 of interest (Klinges et al., 2024). While earlier definitions of microclimate refer to near-ground climate
167 at high temporal and spatial resolution, the term proximal climate emphasizes the importance of
168 biological/ecological relevance (proximity) of the climate to an organism etc. in models linking climate
169 and ecological processes/patterns. For instance, the proximal microclimate for an arboreal frog would
170 be the climatic conditions in the tree canopy, whereas the proximal microclimate for an earthworm
171 would be soil temperature and moisture conditions in the upper 10 cm of the soil.

172 **Vapour Pressure Deficit (VPD):** VPD is the difference between the *saturation vapour pressure* (i.e.
173 water vapour pressure in fully saturated air at a given temperature) and the *actual vapour pressure* of
174 water in the air. In other words, it quantifies the “drying power” or atmospheric demand for moisture
175 (Jones, 2014).

176

177 **Box 2: The physics of microclimate**

178 Microclimates are created in the process of energy exchange between the ground, water, vegetation,
179 and the air (**Fig. 3**). Incoming sunlight (solar/shortwave **radiation**) and heat (thermal/longwave
180 radiation) are split into energy that warms surfaces (**sensible heat**), inducing phase change such as
181 evaporating water (**latent heat**), or is **stored** in the ground and vegetation. This balance of energy
182 explains differences in surface and air temperature (Chen et al., 1999; Oke, 1987).

183 **Net radiation** is the sum of incoming and outgoing radiation, comprising both shortwave and
184 long wave thermal radiation. Radiation is either absorbed or reflected by surfaces or partially
185 transmitted through vegetation, with dense canopy reducing the amount of solar radiation that reaches
186 the ground. Natural surfaces mainly absorb incoming shortwave radiation from the sun and re-emit
187 energy as longwave radiation. Net radiation is typically positive during the day (i.e., more radiation
188 enters the system) and negative at night (i.e., more radiation exits the system, but more stable over day-
189 and-night below canopy than above it (Baldocchi & Vogel, 1996; Ross, 1975) leading to microclimate
190 buffering. Net radiation is further partitioned into sensible heat flux, latent heat flux, and heat storage

191 (Fig. 3). **Sensible heat**, which results in a change of temperature of a substance, represents the energy
192 transferred from warm surfaces to the overlying air by conduction and convection. Conduction transfers
193 heat within or between materials (e.g. between soil and air) due to direct molecular collision and occurs
194 at the immediate interface - the thin boundary layer of air in contact with the surface. Convection then
195 carries that heat away from the surface (or toward it) via bulk air movement. Convection can be driven
196 merely by density differences (warm light-weighted air rises) or forced by, e.g., wind. **Latent heat** is
197 the energy required to change a substance's phase, such as water from liquid to vapour and is driven by
198 a combination of evaporation and transpiration.

199 The rate of both sensible and latent heat exchange between the surface and the air is governed
200 by temperature or vapour pressure difference between the two, and by wind speed, which determines
201 how efficiently heat or moisture is **advected**, i.e., transported away by moving air (Lewis & Randall,
202 1923). Latent heat transfer is additionally regulated by the opening and closing of leaf stomata in
203 response to photosynthetically active radiation as well as other environmental and physiological cues
204 such as vapour pressure deficit, temperature, CO₂ concentration, and plant water status. Wind speed is
205 influenced strongly by landscape features such as terrain and vegetation, being lower closer to the
206 ground surface, where wind speeds are reduced owing to surface drag. Thus, in forest understories and
207 other sheltered environments, sensible and latent fluxes are reduced due to lower wind speeds and
208 suppressed turbulence, contributing to the thermal decoupling of below-canopy microclimates from
209 above-canopy macroclimatic conditions (Baldocchi & Vogel, 1996; Finnigan, 2000).

210 These fluxes are temperature-dependent, and surface temperature can thus be estimated by
211 assuming an equilibrium state is reached. In reality, the ground accumulates heat during the day or
212 growing season and releases it at night and in winter. To account for this, an additional term representing
213 energy storage and release (mainly in the soil, but also in vegetation and water) is included in the energy
214 balance, helping to reconcile flux imbalances over daily and seasonal timescales (Choudhury et al.,
215 1987). Soil water content has a pronounced effect on rates of soil heat storage as wetter soils have higher
216 thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity and thus wet soils will typically store more heat,
217 dampening temperature fluctuations (Campbell & Norman, 2012).

218 Beyond localised energy fluxes, **mesoclimate**-scale processes shape fine-scale climatic
219 variation through the lateral movement and mixing of air across landscapes (Barry & Chorley, 2009).
220 Elevation affects temperature via the adiabatic **lapse rate** (vertical rate at which atmospheric
221 temperature decreases with elevation), modulated by air humidity, and influenced by terrain and wind
222 (Barry, 2008; Lookingbill & Urban, 2003). On clear, calm nights, when the atmosphere is stable, dense
223 air can sink into valleys, resulting in **cold-air pooling** (i.e., the accumulation of cold, dense air in
224 topographic depressions), which locally reverses lapse rates (creating temperature inversions) and
225 creates frost pockets. **Proximity to water bodies** also moderates temperature extremes, as water's high
226 heat capacity slows heating and cooling, with inland influence depending on wind, topography, and

227 surface roughness. Thus both meso- and micro-scale processes generate complex spatial patterns in
228 near-surface climate and warming rates.

229
230 *Fig. 3. (in Box 2) Main components of the energy exchange between the Earth surface, vegetation, and*
231 *atmosphere that shape microclimate variation across space and time (here for simplicity ignoring*
232 *lateral heat transfer, such as cold-air pooling). Microclimate conditions arise from the balance between*
233 *incoming solar (shortwave; SW) radiation and outgoing thermal (longwave; LW) radiation, as well as*
234 *from the partitioning of the net radiation into sensible heat flux, latent heat flux (associated with*
235 *evapotranspiration, condensation, freezing, and melting), and the storage or release of heat within soil*
236 *and vegetation. Net radiation is usually positive during the day (a) and negative during the night (b).*
237 *The radiation balance and energy fluxes are influenced by meteorological conditions - such as clouds*
238 *or air humidity - and by land surface features - such as topography, vegetation structure and soil*
239 *moisture - thereby mediating local microclimatic variability and its divergence from broader*
240 *macroclimate conditions.*

241

242 PART I: Changing meteorological conditions

243 In this chapter, we will discuss some mechanisms by which changes in meteorological conditions
244 (caused by climate change) will change microclimate landscapes by causing microclimates to diverge
245 (increased heterogeneity) or converge (homogenization). In order to illustrate single mechanisms, we
246 discuss meteorological variables one by one and present their simulated effects on microclimate
247 independently from other variables (See also results from case study 1 in **Fig. 6** and **Fig. 7** and
248 Supplementary Information). In reality, however, many of these variables can change in parallel (e.g.,
249 cloud cover, rainfall and soil moisture) and realistic rates of microclimate change can only be predicted
250 by modelling the changes in all variables in concert (**Fig. 1**) (Maclean, 2020).

251 2. Macroclimate temperature

252 2.1 General increase of air temperature

253 A rise in macroclimate temperature alone leads to an increase in the emission of longwave radiation,
254 thereby perhaps counterintuitively reducing the rate at which near-ground microclimate warms relative
255 to macroclimate (see Part III). Rising temperatures also increase the atmospheric demand for water,
256 thus enhancing **vapour pressure deficit (VPD)** and consequently potential evapotranspiration (Novick
257 et al., 2024). How this translates into actual evapotranspiration depends on local soil moisture and
258 vegetation response and can shift dynamically (Wetzel & Chang, 1987). In moist sites, evaporation and
259 transpiration can increase with increasing temperature and VPD, and latent heat flux further slows down
260 surface warming (**Fig. 6 j-l**). However, enhanced evaporation and transpiration also accelerate soil
261 drying. As vapor pressure deficit rises and stomata close to limit water loss, evapotranspiration
262 declines and a larger share of energy is converted to sensible heat, leading to accelerated surface
263 warming. These mechanisms thus create potentially divergent warming trajectories between wet and
264 dry(ing) microenvironments (Seneviratne et al., 2010; Srivastava et al., 2024). For example, García-
265 García et al. (2023) found that soil temperatures during annual heat extremes were rising faster than air
266 temperatures in two-thirds of their European measurement sites, which they attributed to declining soil
267 moisture and associated heat-amplifying feedbacks, such as reduced latent heat transfer and decreased
268 specific heat capacity of dry soil. Additionally, land generally warms faster than oceans and is predicted
269 to continue to do so (Byrne & O’Gorman, 2018) causing coastal regions to warm more slowly than
270 inland areas (Al-Ruzouq et al., 2022; IPCC, 2023). In both cases, the difference between wet and dry
271 sites or the difference between land and water can potentially lead to different rates of warming,
272 increasing micro- and mesoclimate variability across landscapes.

273

274 2.3 Lapse rates and their role in mesoclimate warming patterns

275 The adiabatic lapse rate - the rate at which air temperature decreases with altitude - plays a critical role
276 in determining how warming is distributed vertically through the atmosphere and how much of that
277 warming is expressed at the surface. In the troposphere, the lower layer of the atmosphere, temperature
278 typically declines with altitude as rising air expands and cools under lower pressure. The actual rate of
279 decline, however, depends on the moisture content of the air: in dry air, the adiabatic lapse rate creates
280 a steep temperature gradient, while in moist air condensation releases latent heat and reduces the rate
281 of cooling with altitude. Because water vapour content varies across regions and over time, lapse rates
282 are not uniform, and this means that neighbouring sites, e.g., those at different elevations, can
283 experience different rates of microclimate warming even under the same regional macroclimate (**Fig.**
284 **4a**). For instance, Chan et al. (2024) used the laws of thermodynamics to map the adiabatic lapse rate

285 across all mountain regions globally. They reported values ranging from 2.94 to 8.09 °C per km,
 286 depending on water vapour content, with the steepest lapse rates in the Himalayas, due to a combination
 287 of dry and cold air. By combining this global map with data on temporal rates of change in mean annual
 288 temperature during the period 1971-2020, they mapped the vertical velocities of isotherm shifts across
 289 mountain regions. Reported values of vertical climate velocities ranged from 1.81 m per year to 10.83 m
 290 per year, with the highest velocities found in dry areas as well as in wet regions with shallow lapse rates
 291 - for example, northern Sumatra, the Brazilian highlands and southern Africa. These spatial, and
 292 potentially temporal, variations in the lapse rate can either amplify or dampen surface warming,
 293 depending on the region, season, and local climatic conditions (**Fig. 4a**). For instance, in parts of
 294 Europe, like the Mediterranean, stronger near-surface summer warming compared to the global average
 295 has been observed, and this enhanced surface warming has been linked in part to steeper lapse rates,
 296 meaning a more rapid temperature decline with altitude (Brogli et al., 2021).

297 From a mesoclimate perspective, changes in the lapse rate mean that mountain tops may warm
 298 at different rates than nearby lowlands, even if free-air warming is spatially uniform (Pepin et al., 2022).
 299 Additionally, in areas with complex topography, vertical mixing of air masses becomes more important,
 300 and altered lapse rates can influence the stability of the lower atmosphere, affecting both temperature
 301 inversions and the likelihood of cold-air pooling (see below). Therefore, changes in the lapse rate are a
 302 key atmospheric mechanism contributing to spatial heterogeneity in warming rates across landscapes at
 303 mesoclimate scales.

304

305

306 **Fig. 4.** Different rates of warming caused by changes in lapse rate and cold-air pooling/inversion. a) The black
 307 line shows a normal lapse rate, which is typical for the mixed troposphere. The right grey line represents a steeper
 308 lapse rate, which can occur under conditions of enhanced surface warming (e.g., due to drying or soil moisture
 309 loss). As the lapse rate steepens, more of the warming is concentrated near the surface, leading to stronger
 310 warming at low elevations. This explains why areas with the same amount of atmospheric heating can experience
 311 different surface temperature responses - a key mechanism behind mesoclimate variation in warming rates. b)
 312 The black line shows a typical temperature profile during an inversion. If the conditions under which inversions
 313 form become less frequent (grey line), sites in different elevations may experience different rates of warming.

314 2.4 Temperature inversions and cold-air pooling

315 Temperature inversions - where air temperature increases with altitude rather than decreasing - are
316 key mechanism influencing near-ground temperatures. Inversions at the earth's surface typically form
317 under calm, clear-sky night time conditions following sunny daytime warm surfaces that promote strong
318 nocturnal radiative cooling of the ground, resulting in a dense cold air layer trapped beneath warm air.
319 The strength (temperature gradient) and depth (vertical extent) of these surface inversions determine
320 how much they insulate the ground from warmer overlying air. Climate change is altering the frequency
321 and characteristics of these inversions. A global trend towards shallower inversions, with regional level
322 variable changes in inversion strength has been observed between 1989 and 2019 (H. Zeng et al., 2022).
323 In the Arctic, a particularly strong decline in inversion depth has been observed - due to the combined
324 effects of sea ice loss and increased cloud cover, both of which reduce surface radiative cooling (Ruman
325 et al., 2022; L. Zhang et al., 2021).

326 More localized surface temperature inversions are caused by cold-air drainage and pooling, a
327 process in which cooler, denser air flows downslope under gravity and accumulates in topographic
328 depressions (**Fig. 4b**). This pooling can lead to strong and frequent near-surface inversions, particularly
329 in mountainous or forested areas (Daly et al., 2010). Cold-air pooling is therefore best understood as a
330 specific, landscape-driven subset of surface inversions, one that is tightly coupled to local topography
331 and land cover. For instance, under forest canopies downslope cold-air drainage can persist during the
332 daytime thanks to the decoupling between canopy and sub-canopy microclimatic conditions (Pypker et
333 al., 2007), while in treeless areas cold-air drainage occurs typically only during the night-time.

334 The occurrence and strength of cold-air pooling - and hence its influence on microclimate - is
335 sensitive to climate change. Decreasing cloudiness may promote more frequent and intense cold-air
336 pooling due to enhanced night-time cooling, while increasing cloud cover can suppress it. Similarly,
337 changes in wind speed and direction can either disrupt or enhance cold-air pooling events depending on
338 local exposure and terrain configuration (Miró et al., 2018). These interactions mean that cold-air
339 pooling-prone areas, such as forested slopes and closed basins, may experience slower rates of warming
340 compared to adjacent open sites (Daly et al., 2010; Pastore et al., 2022). Conversely, in regions where
341 temperature inversions are weakening due to increased cloudiness or reduced snow cover (as cold air
342 forms over snow patches), warming may accelerate (**Fig. 4b**). In this way, shifts in the frequency,
343 strength, and spatial distribution of temperature inversions can contribute to increase the heterogeneity
344 in microclimate warming rates across the landscape.

345 Current evidence for different rates of climate warming due to cold-air pooling is mixed. Using
346 45 years of observational data from multiple meteorological stations in a forested mountain watershed,
347 (Jones et al., 2025) found little variation in multi-decadal climate trends among sites, despite frequent
348 occurrences of cold-air pooling and temperature inversions. (Hiebl & Schöner, 2018), on the other hand,
349 exploited a gridded observational dataset of daily minimum temperature across Austria over the 1961-

350 2017 period and found that winter inversions had declined in frequency by 11% leading to accelerated
351 warming rates at low elevations. This illustrates the strong context dependency and therefore the need
352 to better understand how changes in mesoclimatic conditions affect microclimatic changes over longer
353 periods.

354

355 3. Clouds

356 Changes in cloud cover - including timing, altitude, and extent - strongly affect local radiation balances,
357 thereby shaping microclimate warming patterns. On clear summer days with high incoming solar
358 radiation, temperature contrasts between adjacent microclimates peak due to spatial differences in
359 shortwave radiation (Maclean et al., 2021). Low-altitude clouds, like stratus and cumulus, block
360 incoming solar radiation, thereby reducing spatial temperature contrasts near the surface. Observed and
361 projected trends show that global average daytime cloud fraction decreases faster than night-time cloud
362 fraction (Luo et al., 2024b), but that there is a large variability across regions and seasons, as well as a
363 high uncertainty in predictions due to cloud-atmosphere feedbacks (Hou et al., 2021).

364 Reductions in daytime cloud cover such as those reported over Central Europe (Sfică et al.,
365 2021) increase the amount of sunlight reaching the surface. This accelerates warming on sun-exposed
366 slopes compared to slowly-warming shaded, pole-facing slopes, increasing their contrast in near-ground
367 temperature (Chesnoiu et al., 2025) (**Fig. 5, Fig. 6 d-f**). The effect occurs not only in mountains but also
368 in moderately complex terrains at low sun angles, especially at higher latitudes (Guthrie, 2001), or
369 independent of topography across canopy cover gradients (Grimmond et al., 2000; Johnson & Smith,
370 2008) or urban to rural transitions (Cheung & Jim, 2019; Unger, 1996). The magnitude of this
371 asymmetry depends on cloud thickness, sun angle, and surface albedo (e.g., from snow, soil, or
372 vegetation).

373 Clouds also play a key role at night. While daytime temperature contrasts are largely driven by
374 incoming solar radiation, night-time cooling is governed by thermal longwave radiation loss to the sky.
375 Clouds absorb and emit longwave radiation back to the ground (this is the reason why clear nights are
376 often colder than cloudy nights), inhibiting cold-air formation and pooling in topographic depressions
377 (**Fig. 5**) and generally homogenizing temperatures across a landscape (**Fig. 7 d-f**). For example, Groot
378 & Carlson (1996) found the difference of near-ground night temperatures between open environments
379 and under shelterwood to be larger in calm clear-sky nights compared to nights with an overcast sky.

380

381

382 *Figure 5. Reductions in daytime cloud cover cause nearby microclimates to diverge over time, increasing*
 383 *microclimate variance across space. With decreasing cloudiness, open meadows warm faster than forest*
 384 *interiors (a) and sun-exposed slopes warm faster than shaded slopes (b). c) Warming trajectories of adjacent*
 385 *microclimates with different warming trends (bright vs. dark triangle, meadow vs. forest interior in a and*
 386 *sun-exposed vs. shaded slope in b). d) Visualizes a possible scenario where macroclimate temperature increases and*
 387 *cloudiness decreases over three time steps (now, +5 yrs, +10 yrs), thereby increasing microclimate contrasts*
 388 *over short distances (bright triangles vs. dark triangle).*

389

390 4. Precipitation

391 One facet of climate change is shifts in the amount, timing, frequency, and intensity of precipitation
 392 (Calvin et al., 2023) and, linked to that, the amount of moisture in the soil and humidity in the air.

393 While the impact of changes in precipitation on soil moisture may depend strongly on climate regime,
 394 topography, vegetation, and soil type, more precipitation generally leads to increases in soil moisture
 395 (Cowley et al., 2017; Litaor et al., 2008); (Sehler et al., 2019). Soil moisture is an important driver of
 396 near-ground air and soil temperatures, especially under generally warm conditions (Ashcroft & Gollan,
 397 2013; von Arx et al., 2013). When soils are dry, most of the incoming solar energy is converted into
 398 sensible heat, warming the soil surface and the overlying air, rather than being used for evaporation.
 399 Conversely, when soils are wet, a larger fraction of the available energy is converted into latent heat
 400 fluxes (evaporation), and because wet soils have higher thermal conductivity and heat capacity, they
 401 also moderate temperature fluctuations. This generally results in lower daytime and higher night-time
 402 near-ground air temperatures compared to dry conditions (Davis et al., 2019; García-García et al., 2023).
 403 These effects will, however, depend on the ecosystem's soil moisture levels since increasing
 404 precipitation will have larger effects on microclimate in drylands compared to more mesic habitats

405 (Korell et al., 2021). The seasonality of rainfall can also be important for microclimatic conditions. For
406 example, increased summer rainfall generally cools soils by increasing latent heat fluxes and heat
407 capacity (A. Dai et al., 1999; Mengistu et al., 2017). In contrast, changes in winter rainfall do have
408 smaller and more variable effects on soil temperature. Greater winter rainfall, in regions where soils
409 remain unfrozen, can warm soils through higher thermal conductivity and greater heat storage. The
410 magnitude of changes in near-surface microclimatic buffering will also be affected by the extent of
411 intra- and inter-annual variation in precipitation. Areas with pronounced seasonality in rainfall will
412 experience larger seasonal changes in microclimatic buffering in comparison to regions with year-round
413 rainfall. Such variation in precipitation might increase with macroclimate change (W. Zhang et al.,
414 2021), but has been difficult to accurately forecast (van der Wiel & Bintanja, 2021), adding to the
415 uncertainty of predictions of microclimate change.

416 While changes in rainfall are often considered, other forms of precipitation also exhibit
417 temporal trends and influence microclimatic conditions. For example, there is a global reduction in fog
418 (Klemm & Lin, 2016) and dew (Dou et al., 2021), though with exceptions (Lavigne & Liu, 2022).
419 Particularly in arid systems, regular fog events decrease evapotranspiration (thus latent heat fluxes) and
420 drought risk (Baguskas et al., 2016), while also shaping microclimate conditions by attenuating solar
421 radiation, increasing relative humidity and buffering thermal extremes (Sotomayor & Drezner, 2019).
422 Fog buffers minimum temperatures (Y.-J. Zhang et al., 2014), and a decrease in fog would likely lead
423 to higher microclimate variability, including lower minimum temperatures.

424 In cold environments, changes in the depth, timing and duration of snowpacks can have large
425 impacts on microclimates, particularly immediately above and below the snow layer. Due to snow's
426 low thermal conductivity, it forms a strongly insulating layer, decoupling surface temperature from free
427 atmospheric temperature (Aalto et al., 2018). Under snow cover, surface temperatures cannot exceed 0
428 °C because surplus energy input is absorbed as latent heat during melting, effectively buffering the
429 surface against further warming. Therefore, even a thin layer of snow effectively decouples near-ground
430 maximum temperatures from macroclimate maximum temperatures and homogenizes microclimates
431 across a landscape (**Fig. 6 m-o**). Minimum temperatures (below freezing point) below the snow are
432 closely linked to snowpack thickness, with greater snow depth increasing microclimatic buffering up to
433 a threshold depth (often c. 15 - 40 cm; with more compact snow having a lower buffering capacity),
434 beyond which additional snow has limited impact (Wilson et al., 2020; T. Zhang, 2005). Snowpack
435 surfaces are characterised by a higher albedo and, as a result, generally lower near-surface maximum
436 temperatures than adjacent snow-free microsites, with this effect being strongest at high sun angles (T.
437 Zhang, 2005). During low sun angles, on the other hand, experiments show that snow removal reduces
438 winter soil temperatures, as frost penetrates more easily into exposed grounds (Zhao et al., 2022) (**Fig.**
439 **7 m-o**). During snowmelt, sites with thicker snowpack also extend the seasonal soil temperature
440 stability, reducing near-surface frost events, and maintaining higher soil moisture. Thus, the general

441 trend for reduced snowfall and shorter snowpack duration (see, e.g., Calvin et al., 2023), is likely to
442 alter microclimates year-round.

443

444 5. Wind

445 Considerable changes in wind speed and direction have been observed in recent decades, with global
446 patterns showing marked heterogeneity (McVicar et al., 2012). Terrestrial systems have generally
447 experienced wind-stilling (i.e., a decrease in mean wind speed), but trends and projections vary by
448 region (Zha et al., 2021) and may reflect changes in large-scale ocean-atmosphere circulation patterns,
449 such as the North Atlantic Oscillation (Z. Zeng et al., 2019). Wind affects the coupling between ambient
450 and near-surface temperature or humidity by changing the atmospheric mixing close to the ground.
451 Stronger winds enhance convection (see Box 2) as well as vertical and horizontal air mixing, leading to
452 reduced microclimatic heterogeneity and a tighter coupling of micro- to macroclimate fluctuations
453 (Ashcroft et al., 2009; Baker et al., 2021)(**Fig. 7 g-i**). However, this wind-induced homogenization is
454 reduced in forested and topographically complex landscapes, where terrain sheltering and surface
455 roughness limit air mixing (Renaud et al., 2011; Wever, 2012). Thus, increased windiness is expected
456 to reduce microclimate variability most strongly in flat and open landscapes. In our model scenario
457 (case study 1), increased wind speed generally had a cooling effect on maximum temperatures (in
458 agreement with, e.g., Riddell & Porter, 2025), but this cooling effect was weaker under forest canopies
459 compared to open grasslands (**Fig. 6 g-i**). In contrast, windstilling is expected to increase microclimatic
460 extremes by reducing atmospheric mixing, leading to more frequent cold air pooling (Dobrowski, 2011)
461 and more extreme thermal minima (Geiger, 1966). Under windstilling, reduced atmospheric mixing
462 also leads to thicker leaf/surface boundary layers (i.e., the thin layer of air directly adjacent to a surface),
463 decreasing evaporation and likely increasing near surface humidity (H. G. Jones, 2014).

464 Shifts in wind direction (McInnes et al., 2011) may lead to a spatial redistribution of wind-
465 sheltered and wind-exposed microsites, with microsites that become more sheltered from wind
466 potentially experiencing, for example, more extreme temperatures, greater dew accumulation and lower
467 evaporation (Ashcroft et al., 2009; Geiger, 1966; Maclean et al., 2017). Climate models show a large
468 regional variability in projections in annual average and seasonal wind speeds (McInnes et al., 2011)
469 and if any unidirectional long-term trends emerge at all, they are likely very region-specific.

470

471

472

473 *Fig. 6. Model results of case study 1 for maximum near-surface temperature (5 cm above ground),*
 474 *where single meteorological variables (clouds, wind speed, air humidity, and snow cover) were*

475 *modified in isolation to visualize their effect on microclimate warming and how it varies across a 2 ×*
476 *2 km² landscape on the border of Parque Natural Posets Maladeta in the Spanish Pyrenees (See*
477 *Supporting information for more modelling details and an interpretation of observed patterns). Left*
478 *and middle column show the maximum temperature of the 10 warmest days per year when setting the*
479 *respective meteorological variables at low and high values, respectively, and keeping all other*
480 *variables constant. Difference maps (right column) show the differences in between high and low*
481 *simulated values of the meteorological variables, i.e., the effect of going from low to high values. (Icons*
482 *from Flaticon.com)*

483

484

485

486 *Fig. 7. Model results of case study I for minimum near-surface temperature (5 cm above ground), where*
 487 *single meteorological variables (clouds, wind speed, air humidity, and snow cover) were modified in*
 488 *isolation to visualize their effect on microclimate warming and how it varies across a $2 \times 2 \text{ km}^2$*

489 *landscape on the border of Parque Natural Posets Maladeta in the Spanish Pyrenees (See Supporting*
490 *information for more modelling details and an interpretation of observed patterns). Left and middle*
491 *columns show the minimum temperature of the 10 coldest days per year when setting the respective*
492 *meteorological variables at low and high values, respectively, and keeping all other variables constant.*
493 *Difference maps (right column) show the differences in between high and low simulated values of the*
494 *meteorological variables, i.e., the effect of going from low to high values. (Icons from Flaticon.com)*
495

496 PART II: Changes in vegetation

497 The reduction of daily temperature fluctuations (microclimate buffering), often observed under
498 canopies, is primarily influenced by the reflection and absorption of incoming solar radiation during the
499 day, the absorption and emission of outgoing thermal radiation during the night and latent heat fluxes
500 related to evapotranspiration and condensation. Many of these processes depend on structural and
501 physiological properties of the vegetation, such as its canopy height, leaf area index (LAI) and stomatal
502 conductance, i.e., how easily water vapour passes through the stomata on leaf surfaces. (De Frenne et
503 al., 2021). In this chapter, we first focus on physiological and phenological responses of vegetation to
504 macroclimate change that can alter microclimate buffering, while considering vegetation composition
505 constant (i.e., in terms of species, age classes and density), and then discuss microclimate changes
506 caused by changes in plant community composition.

507

508 6. Plant physiology and phenology

509 6.1 Physiological responses to climate change

510 Long-term increases in mean macroclimate temperature can induce physiological and structural
511 adjustments in vegetation that, in turn, change sub-canopy microclimates. In temperature-limited
512 systems such as boreal forests and other high-latitude or high-altitude ecosystems, moderate warming
513 can enhance primary productivity (Piao, Wang, et al., 2019). Rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations
514 may further promote plant growth (Forkel et al., 2016), although this “carbon fertilization effect” is
515 often constrained by nutrient and water availability (Peñuelas et al., 2017; Terrer et al., 2019). Increased
516 productivity typically results in taller, denser and potentially more complex vegetation that transpires
517 more water - when water is not limiting - thereby strengthening the vegetation’s buffering effect on
518 microclimate (Schnabel et al. 2025). Consequently, such vegetation changes can slow down warming
519 of sub-canopy microclimatic maximum temperatures, but potentially speed up the warming of
520 minimum temperatures relative to macroclimate trends (**Fig. 7**). As the relationship between canopy
521 cover or density and sub-canopy temperature is non-linear (**Fig. 7e-f**), the effect of canopy becoming

522 denser or thinner is stronger for vegetation with a less dense canopy (low LAI) compared to a denser
523 canopy (high LAI) where changes in canopy cover or density on minimum and maximum temperature
524 are marginal (Zellweger et al., 2019).

525 Climate change and the associated increase in extreme climatic events can trigger rapid
526 physiological responses in plants (Bertolino et al., 2019; Wahid et al., 2007), as even minor
527 environmental fluctuations may prompt immediate responses. Thermal acclimation, particularly at the
528 leaf level, involves traits such as cuticle thickening, tighter stomatal regulation, and the synthesis of
529 heat-tolerant enzymes. These adaptations help maintain water balance and enzymatic function under
530 heat stress, allowing plants to persist and sustain photosynthesis during warming events (Liu et al.,
531 2024; Wahid et al., 2007). This persistence of vegetation under warming can provide some buffering
532 against macroclimatic fluctuations, although the reduced evapotranspiration associated with thicker
533 cuticles and lower stomatal density (Fernández et al., 2017) can limit the effectiveness of this buffering
534 (Wright & Francia, 2024).

535 However, these mechanisms operate within limits. Once critical temperature thresholds are
536 surpassed, leaf mortality and crown dieback can occur, causing a partial or complete breakdown of
537 microclimate buffering (Doughty et al., 2023; Kopáček et al., 2020). Under drought conditions,
538 restricted soil water availability further limits leaf cooling capacity, as stomatal closure reduces
539 transpiration and photosynthesis to prevent hydraulic failure (Grossiord et al., 2020; Slot et al., 2024).
540 This decline in evaporative cooling weakens vegetation's thermal buffering and increases vulnerability
541 to temperature extremes, often leading to early leaf senescence and canopy dieback (Jump et al., 2017;
542 von Arx et al., 2013). Nonetheless, recent studies have shown that elevated transpiration rates can persist
543 during heatwaves even when carbon uptake ceases, under both well-watered and drought-stressed
544 conditions (Marchin et al., 2023; Posch et al., 2024). This decoupling between transpiration and
545 photosynthesis facilitates thermal regulation of the plant during heat stress. A deeper understanding of
546 these diverse vegetation responses to climatic extremes - and their consequent effects on microclimate
547 - is essential for improving predictions of ecosystem resilience under ongoing climate change.

548

549 6.2 Phenology responses to climate change

550 On an interannual scale, climate change has been shown to alter phenological cycles (e.g., leaf onset,
551 flowering time, leaf shedding) across a wide range of plant groups (Badeck et al., 2004; Inouye, 2022;
552 Piao, Liu, et al., 2019). Warmer winters and springs can advance leaf onset, thereby reducing the rate
553 at which microclimates change relative to the macroclimate. In our second case study, earlier spring
554 leaf out led to a warming of minimum temperatures, while maximum temperatures were cooling (**Fig.**
555 **8**). In cold environments, warming generally extends the leaf-on period (Cai et al., 2025; Piao, Liu, et
556 al., 2019), whereas in warmer regions, leaf shedding may also occur earlier, shortening the growing

557 season (J. Dai et al., 2014). In a mountainous region of Oregon (USA), Ward et al. (2018) observed that
 558 years with weather conditions resembling future climate scenarios - characterized by reduced snowpack
 559 and more frequent high-pressure systems - led to earlier and more synchronized spring phenology across
 560 elevation gradients, reducing microclimatic heterogeneity along this gradient. Phenological shifts can
 561 also create temporal mismatches with macroclimatic seasonal dynamics, as the period of strongest
 562 canopy buffering may no longer coincide with peak solar radiation, thereby diminishing the
 563 effectiveness of microclimate buffering during the hottest part of the year.

564

565

566 *Fig. 8. Model results of case study 2 showing the influence of changes in leaf phenology on microclimate*
 567 *change in a mixed forest in New Hampshire, USA. Observed mean monthly values of the leaf area index*
 568 *(LAI) in April between 1982 and 2019 (a) were used as an input to model forest understory minimum*
 569 *temperature (b) and maximum temperature (c), all else - including macroclimate - being held constant.*

570

571 7. Plant community composition

572 Climate change is reshaping the distribution of plant species (Lenoir et al., 2020), which not only
 573 reshuffles community composition but also the relative abundance of species with direct consequences
 574 on microclimatic processes. Whenever climate change induces turnover in plant communities or a shift
 575 in individuals' abundance or cover, local microclimates can be impacted through changes in vegetation
 576 structure, albedo and/or transpiration. One of the best documented examples of this vegetation-mediated
 577 microclimate change is the "shrubification", i.e., the expansion of woody species into previously

578 treeless ecosystems, such as tundra (Sturm et al., 2001) or savannah (Devine et al., 2017) landscapes
579 (**Fig 9**). The replacement of herbaceous species by woody ones or the increase in woody species
580 abundance dramatically changes vegetation density, height, leaf area, transpiration and albedo (Finne
581 et al., 2023; Mekonnen et al., 2021), which modifies energy fluxes near the ground and therefore the
582 whole temperature regime (Wilcox et al., 2024). However, microclimatic effects of shrubification are
583 complex, with warmer soil temperatures during the winter through, e.g., thermal insulation of the
584 canopy (**Fig. 9j-l**) or thicker snow layers, but cooler soil temperatures in summer through increased
585 radiation interception and transpiration (Kempainen, Niittynen, Virkkala, et al., 2021; Kropp et al.,
586 2021; Myers-Smith & Hik, 2013). In our case study 3, we observed a reduction in maximum
587 temperature by up to 10°C and an increase in minimum temperature under canopies after a vegetation
588 shift from grassland to a steppe woodland (**Fig 9**). Below, we describe in more detail some of the main
589 mechanisms of vegetation-induced changes in microclimate.

590

591 7.1 Vegetation structure

592 Plant species influence microclimatic conditions through their structural characteristics, which can be
593 partly described by traits such as maximum canopy height, cover, and shade-casting ability (Gril,
594 Spicher, et al., 2023; Meeussen et al., 2021). Species favored by climate change can affect microclimate
595 in various ways, but those that are morphologically or phenologically distinct from the original
596 community - such as alien trees invading shrublands or shifts from evergreen to deciduous dominance
597 - are likely to produce stronger microclimatic alterations (Garcia & Clusella-Trullas, 2019). In addition,
598 species forming dense stands can alter the spatial heterogeneity of microclimates (Carter et al., 2015).
599 For instance, in low-growing shrublands, moderate densities of alien trees lowered near-surface air
600 temperatures by increasing shading, whereas dense invasions raised near-surface temperatures by
601 suppressing native ground cover and exposing more bare ground (Garcia & Clusella-Trullas, 2019).
602 Furthermore, forests are rapidly transforming under climate change, with disturbances like droughts,
603 bark beetle outbreaks, fires, and storms driving the most extensive disruptions in 170 years (Senf &
604 Seidl, 2021). These events reduce canopy buffering, causing sub-canopy temperatures to rise rapidly,
605 effectively erasing decades of thermal decoupling (i.e., slower microclimate warming than
606 macroclimate warming) and exposing the understory to thermal conditions equivalent to several years
607 of free-air macroclimate warming (Greiser et al., 2025; Haesen et al., 2025)

608

609 7.2 Surface albedo

610 Species favored by climate change can differ in albedo, thereby altering the amount of solar radiation
611 absorbed at the surface. For instance, birch (*Betula*) exhibits a higher albedo than spruce (*Picea*) in
612 boreal forests (Aartsma et al., 2020; Lukeš et al., 2013). Beyond species-level shifts, large-scale arctic

613 and alpine greening has emerged as a major trend at high latitudes and elevations, driven by warming
614 and a lengthened growing season (Choler et al., 2021; Roland et al., 2024; Rumpf et al., 2022). In these
615 regions, open land is typically snow-covered in winter or lichen-dominated in summer, both
616 characterized by high albedo. However, shrub-dominated communities can have albedo values up to
617 twice as low as the lichen *Cladonia stellaris* in mountainous Norway (Aartsma et al., 2020), thereby
618 enhancing microclimate warming through increased absorption of solar radiation (Mallen-Cooper et al.,
619 2021). Conversely, in warmer regions, rising temperatures and declining precipitation may promote
620 desertification, where reduced vegetation cover relative to bare ground increases surface albedo (IPCC,
621 2022).

622

623 7.3 Transpiration

624 Many species replacing current assemblages possess morphological and hydraulic traits that enhance
625 their ability to cope with new climatic conditions (Kramp et al., 2022; Kühn et al., 2021). In some alpine
626 meadows, colonizing lowland species exhibit larger leaves (Debouk et al., 2015; Schuchardt et al.,
627 2023), which increase transpiration rates, elevate air humidity, and reduce temperatures through latent
628 heat exchange - though only in ecosystems where water availability is not limiting. In regions facing
629 more frequent droughts, however, “winner” species are likely to be characterized by short stature, sparse
630 canopies, small and thick leaves, and reduced stomatal density or tighter stomatal regulation to
631 minimize water loss. As drought intensity and frequency increase, the dominance of such water-
632 conserving species may diminish the vegetation’s cooling potential (Michalet et al., 2024; Richter et
633 al., 2022). Nonetheless, these species can delay soil water depletion and slow subsequent microclimate
634 warming and drying (Teuling et al., 2010). Moreover, drought-adapted species often possess deep root
635 systems (Kühn et al., 2021), increasing their resilience to climatic extremes and enabling partial
636 maintenance of canopy cover - and thus microclimate buffering - even under prolonged drought stress.

637

638 7.4 Species diversity

639 The impact of climate change on plant community richness is highly context-dependent (Cowles et al.,
640 2018; Ronk et al., 2020). In cold regions at high elevations and latitudes, ongoing increases in plant
641 diversity (Steinbauer et al., 2018; Suggitt et al., 2019) may enhance canopy density and rooting depth
642 diversity, leading to higher evapotranspiration rates and stronger microclimate buffering where water
643 availability is sufficient (Kunert et al., 2012; Schnabel et al., 2025; S. Zhang et al., 2022). Higher species
644 diversity also enhances community stability and resilience to extreme events (De Boeck et al., 2018;
645 Tilman & Downing, 1994). Consequently, greater species richness or functional diversity within the
646 vegetation layer can promote more buffered microclimatic conditions and, in turn, enhance ecosystem
647 functioning and stability (Beugnon et al., 2024; Huang et al., 2024).

648

649 *Fig. 9. Model results of case study 3, where we modelled the effect of increased tree and shrub cover*
 650 *on minimum and maximum near-ground air temperature (5 cm above ground) in a 1 x 1 km² grassland*
 651 *area in the Central Anatolian Steppe of Niğde Province, western Turkey. Invasion of shrubs and trees*
 652 *was modelled by superimposing structural vegetation data such as canopy height (f) and leaf area*
 653 *index, LAI (e) from a nearby steppe-woodland site onto a digital terrain model of the grassland site (d).*
 654 *(g-l) Minimum and maximum temperatures (at 5 cm above ground) refer to average of daily minimum*
 655 *and maximum temperatures of the years' 10 coldest or hottest days, respectively. (i and l) Temperature*
 656 *difference between the grassland and the woodland scenario, negative (blue) values mean temperatures*
 657 *are getting cooler.*

658 PART III: Feedbacks

659 8. Vegetation and microclimate feedbacks

660 The global climate is regulated by both negative and positive feedbacks that either dampen or amplify
661 further warming, caused by increased greenhouse gas emissions (IPCC, 2023; Wolff et al., 2015). Near-
662 surface temperature- and moisture conditions as well as vegetation responses to climate change are
663 important parts of these feedback processes. Among the most fundamental stabilizing influences is the
664 Planck feedback whereby warming surfaces emit more thermal energy, thereby enhancing energy loss
665 and preventing unchecked warming. This negative feedback maintains the coupling of microclimate to
666 macroclimate and sustains the biosphere's energy balance (IPCC, 2023). Additionally, as surfaces
667 warm, their capacity to dissipate heat through enhanced convective exchange with the atmosphere
668 increases, further buffering local conditions by reducing the increase in microclimate temperatures
669 compared to macroclimate warming. However, the strength of these feedbacks varies regionally and is
670 influenced by interactions with atmospheric moisture and cloud formation, potentially altering their
671 effectiveness.

672 As the atmosphere warms, its capacity to hold moisture increases as well as potential
673 evaporation rates from vegetation and soils, independently from changes in the vegetation. Since water
674 vapor is a potent greenhouse gas, it can enhance the greenhouse effect through a positive climate
675 feedback, leading to further warming at both macro- and microclimatic scales (IPCC, 2023). However,
676 clouds strongly regulate this positive feedback by limiting the amount of solar radiation reaching the
677 surface, thereby constraining local warming through a negative feedback. Changes in surface albedo
678 also exert strong feedbacks on climate. The loss of bright, reflective surfaces, such as ice, snow, and
679 clouds, increases microclimate temperatures and ultimately reinforces warming through a positive
680 feedback (Bright et al., 2014; Jiao et al., 2017). Climate change has led to an overall decreasing trend
681 in albedo via increases in vegetation cover and decreases in seasonal snow. This can have positive
682 feedbacks to the macroclimate and can also enhance extreme weather events (Evans et al., 2017;
683 Pearson et al., 2013; Pecl et al., 2017).

684 Vegetation dynamics further modify these physical feedbacks by altering energy exchange
685 between the land surface and the atmosphere (De Frenne et al., 2021; Miralles et al., 2025).
686 Photosynthetically active vegetation under adequate moisture conditions regulates microclimate
687 through transpiration, cooling the plant canopy surface and nearby air, and promoting cloud formation,
688 which can reflect solar radiation, cooling near-surface temperature even further (Duveiller et al., 2021).
689 Conversely, loss of vegetation cover driven by, e.g., drought-induced reductions in soil moisture or
690 more direct sunburn due to intense and repeated heatwaves, limits evapotranspiration, allowing the
691 surface to heat more rapidly (IPCC, 2023). Changes in vegetation cover can further alter cloud cover

692 formation (Duveiller et al., 2021) through an increase or a decrease in emissions of biogenic volatile
693 organic compounds (BVOCs) (Greenberg et al., 2004; Rap et al., 2018). For example, Dada et al. (2023)
694 demonstrated that BVOCs, largely emitted by tropical trees, play a big role in biogenic nucleation,
695 providing condensation nuclei for cloud formation. Likewise, cloud glaciation (cloud droplets
696 becoming ice) and precipitation is directly driven by atmospheric pollen release (Kretzschmar et al.,
697 2024). Trees and shrubs have been shown to increase germination, survival and growth of new trees
698 and shrubs by elevating night-time temperatures (D’Odorico et al., 2013). These vegetation-
699 microclimate feedbacks therefore likely control the position of tree-lines (i.e., the sharp transitions from
700 woodland to grasslands), which in turn potentially feed back to the global climate via biophysical (e.g.,
701 albedo) or biogeochemical (e.g., BVOCs, greenhouse gases) processes. Wildfire activity, intensified by
702 warming and drying, represents another potent feedback (MacCarthy et al., 2024; Pellegrini et al.,
703 2021). Wildfires release CO₂ and black carbon into the atmosphere, and this may leave behind darker,
704 lower-albedo surfaces, especially when deposited on snow and ice, amplifying both microclimate
705 temperatures and global warming (McCarty et al., 2021). Vegetation loss often causes soil degradation
706 and desertification, leading to soil erosion and depletion of organic matter, as well as changes in surface
707 albedo, all triggering cycles of declining productivity and aridification (IPCC, 2023). These processes
708 weaken local cooling effects and carbon storage capacity.

709 The carbon cycle introduces additional feedbacks on the climate (Arora et al., 2020; Song et
710 al., 2019), many of them being self-reinforcing. While such processes are normally linked to
711 macroclimate, and captured in coarse-gridded earth system models, most are actually regulated by
712 microclimate. A major concern is the release of long-stored CO₂ and methane from thawing permafrost,
713 enhancing atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations and driving further warming (Schuur et al.,
714 2022). Similarly, climate change might induce forest dieback, releasing CO₂ into the atmosphere and
715 thus reinforcing warming (Munday et al., 2025). Negative feedbacks can reduce the buffering capacity
716 of the vegetation on understory microclimate, risking surpassing thermal thresholds for understory
717 biodiversity (Doughty et al., 2023). On the other hand, initial CO₂ fertilization effects, where higher
718 atmospheric CO₂ concentrations stimulate plant growth and carbon uptake, may provide a temporary
719 buffer against rising emissions possibly benefiting plant microclimate (Norby, 2025). However, this
720 effect can saturate over time due to nutrient limitations, drought stress, and ecosystem shifts toward less
721 carbon-dense vegetation (Peñuelas et al., 2017; Terrer et al., 2019). For example, climate change can
722 favour transitions of forests and shrublands to open ecosystems, which typically store less carbon,
723 reinforcing atmospheric CO₂ increases (Rosan et al., 2019; Venter et al., 2018).

724 Interactions among the energy balance, vegetation dynamics, and the carbon cycle form a
725 dynamic system that will strongly influence the trajectory of future climate change. While these
726 processes are much studied at broad spatial extents and coarse spatial resolutions, it is increasingly clear
727 that microclimates at fine spatial resolutions but across large spatial extents may play a critical role in

728 mediating these feedbacks while being affected by them. Microclimates shape the temperature, moisture
729 and radiation environments experienced by individual organisms and vegetation, and in doing so,
730 govern many of the processes that collectively scale up to influence global carbon, water and energy
731 exchanges. Understanding their relative strength, timing, and interactions, and integrating microclimatic
732 processes into broader models of biosphere and atmosphere coupling, is critical for predicting the Earth
733 system's response over the coming decades. Despite the dominance of positive feedback loops, some
734 processes can temporarily slow down global warming. However, many of these negative feedbacks are
735 uncertain, highly regional, and may be offset by processes leading to accelerated warming such as
736 concurrent changes in albedo, water availability, or disturbance regimes.

737

738 9. Conclusions and outlook

739 We explored some of the mechanisms driving long-term microclimate changes, illustrating how
740 changes in macroclimate temperature, cloud cover, precipitation, and wind patterns shape near-surface
741 microclimate conditions over time. We examined how shifting meteorological conditions influence
742 microclimates and how climate-driven vegetation changes alter local microclimate conditions. We also
743 discussed how natural macroclimate-microclimate and/or vegetation feedbacks play a crucial role in
744 shaping future macroclimate change itself, involving both positive feedbacks (e.g., snow and ice loss
745 and resulting albedo shifts that amplify warming) and negative ones (e.g., vegetation greening absorbing
746 more CO₂ and thus slowing warming).

747 In practice, microclimate change in any given ecosystem reflects the combined influence of all
748 of these interacting processes (**Fig. 2**), with the outcome additionally depending on anthropogenic
749 greenhouse gas emissions and land-use modification. As a result, some areas may experience
750 accelerated microclimate warming relative to the pace of macroclimate change, while other areas may
751 experience less microclimate warming or even cooling (Maclean, 2020). Similarly, some regions may
752 exhibit increased spatial heterogeneity, while others become more homogenized—all with significant
753 consequences for physiology, behaviour, population dynamics, and distributions of life on Earth.
754 Ultimately, we hope that this microclimatic perspective on climate change enhances our ability to
755 predict ecological responses in a rapidly changing world, helping researchers and practitioners
756 anticipate and manage impacts at scales relevant to both organisms and ecosystems.

757 While microclimate ecology has recently focused on increasing the spatial resolution of climate
758 datasets, we show here that it is at least equally important to systematically understand and represent
759 temporal dynamics. A key step forward involves the efficient pairing of macroclimate and microclimate
760 time series observations to detect real-world trends and divergences and increase our understanding of
761 microclimate buffering or amplification during climate extremes. The growing availability of long-term

762 microclimate records (Lembrechts et al., 2020) holds great value for capturing fine-scale spatiotemporal
763 patterns that are often obscured in coarse-resolution macroclimate data (Haesen et al., 2025).

764 Microclimate observation can also strategically prioritize data collection that supports the
765 development, refinement, and validation of mechanistic models - such as those we used in this paper -
766 building on available open-source approaches (Buckley et al., 2023; Kearney & Porter, 2017; Maclean,
767 2025). Grounded in physical principles, such models offer a robust framework for simulating changing
768 (micro)climate conditions, to then explore and project ecological responses. Unlike correlative
769 approaches, mechanistic models explicitly represent underlying processes and better extrapolate beyond
770 observed data (Malmborg et al., 2024), making them a more reliable foundation for scenario
771 development and long-term forecasting or hindcasting. Nevertheless, they rely on high-quality in-situ
772 measurements of various microclimate parameters and their drivers (e.g., leaf area index but also leaf
773 angle estimates) for validation, with the latter being rarely measured in conjunction with microclimate
774 at the moment.

775 In parallel, the microclimate community has made impressive progress in producing high-
776 resolution gridded products of microclimate temperature at local (Gril, Laslier, et al., 2023; Niittynen
777 et al., 2024), regional (Greiser et al., 2018), continental (Haesen, Lembrechts, et al., 2023), and global
778 scales (Lembrechts et al., 2022). While these datasets offer broad spatial coverage and accessibility, our
779 assessment underscores the need for cautious use. Many of these maps represent static microclimate
780 landscapes that in reality vary in time and come with substantial uncertainty. Researchers are therefore
781 encouraged to critically evaluate the temporal extent and resolution of these products and to develop
782 new gridded microclimate datasets that integrate both spatial and temporal dynamics (Klinges et al.,
783 2024). By incorporating these practices, ecological research will be better equipped to capture the
784 complexity of climate-ecology interactions and to advance predictive modelling capabilities for the
785 future.

786 Additionally, while this review focuses largely on trends in mean microclimate change, such
787 averages may obscure ecologically critical shifts in the frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme
788 events - often the primary triggers of biological responses like sudden range shifts (Soifer et al., 2025)
789 or ecosystem tipping-points (Lenton, 2013). To apply this understanding, spatiotemporal variation in
790 microclimate must be viewed in the context of historical variability, which defines extremes and shapes
791 species' climatic niches (Janzen, 1967; Nadeau et al., 2017). Importantly, microclimate changes can be
792 spatially heterogeneous, and therefore what constitutes an extreme event at a regional scale (e.g., heat
793 waves or droughts) may be locally amplified or buffered.

794 Because microclimates vary at the spatiotemporal scales relevant to life on Earth, organisms
795 can respond to microclimate change through mechanisms such as thermoregulatory behaviour (Sunday
796 et al., 2014), dispersal and range shifts towards more favourable conditions (Maclean & Early, 2023),
797 and physiological plasticity (Helmuth et al., 2010). These responses are species-specific and influenced

798 by climatic niches and genetic diversity, as well as biotic interactions, which all together can further
799 amplify or buffer the impacts of microclimate change on species, communities, and ecosystems (Wright
800 & Francia, 2024).

801 Finally, we emphasize that much of the foundational knowledge in micrometeorology reviewed
802 here has been established for decades, thanks to early theoretical and empirical work (Geiger, 1966).
803 However, only recently has this knowledge seen substantial uptake in the ecological sciences
804 (Kemppinen et al., 2024). This highlights the urgent need for deeper collaboration and interdisciplinary
805 science between biosciences, atmospheric sciences and earth sciences - essential for understanding how
806 climate change is experienced by organisms and how they will respond. Strengthening these
807 interdisciplinary connections will also help close the loop on how shifting microclimates may, in turn,
808 influence broader climate dynamics.

809

810 Conflict of interest

811 The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

812

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832

833 Supplementary Information

834 The Supplementary Information contains more information on the three modelling scenarios.

835

836 Data availability statement

837 The data that support the modelling scenarios of this study are available upon reasonable request. The
838 R-packages used for the modelling can be accessed under <https://github.com/ilyamaclean/microclimf>
839 and <https://github.com/ilyamaclean/micropoint>.

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